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Using Ceramics for the Transformation of Contemporary Art: Lv Pinchang's Departure and Return

Shang Hui

The white marble group sculpture *Faith*, which stands on the west square of the Museum of the Communist Party of China, is a monumental example of public art, embodying the ideological spirit of the new era. As the chief artist of this group sculpture, Lv Pinchang led the sculpture team from the Central Academy of Fine Arts (CAFA) through three years of arduous exploration and made numerous revisions, so that the work not only typically portrays the numerous heroic models who fought bravely for faith in the hundred-year history of the Party, but also demonstrates the extremely powerful faith force inherent in the hundred-year struggle of the Party through the solemn expressions of those swearing allegiance to the Party that are continuously presented in the group sculpture. This group sculpture has addressed several difficult problems well, such as properly handling the individualized image depiction of heroic prototypes, the connection and organic combination of numerous figures in the group sculpture from front to back, and making the fist-clenching and swearing postures both full of momentum and mutually responsive, thus creating the overall sense of movement in this large-scale group sculpture.

It should be said that the artistic level and achievements of *Faith* reflect the rich practical experience accumulated by Lv Pinchang, the chief artist, and his consistent pursuit of art. As early as the mid-1990s, Lv Pinchang followed senior sculptor Cheng Yunxian to successively complete a series of works, including *A Generation of Heroes* in the August 1 Nanchang Uprising Memorial Hall, *Towards Victory* in Zao Garden in Yan'an and *Liberate the Whole of China* in the Military Museum. During this process, Lv Pinchang accumulated experience in character prototype accumulation for thematic sculptures and realistic sculpture creation.

After that, he created a number of monumental sculpture masterpieces, such as the bronze reliefs *Jinggang Meeting* and *Red Capital Ruiji* in Nanchang August 1 Square, *On the Road to Guangchang* at

the north gate of the Soviet Area, and *Sending Off the Husband to Join the Army, Looking Forward and Planting Planks and Dividing Land* in Jinggang Martyrs Cemetery. At the turn of the century, he participated in the creation project of *The Chinese People's War of Resistance Against Japanese Aggression Memorial Group Sculpture* and completed the design and creation of two groups of sculptures, *Great Sword Majesty* and *Bullets and Bombs*.

In terms of single-figure portrait creation the sculptor's ability to depict characters is most evident, because not only is it necessary to achieve a resemblance but it is also necessary to explore the inner world of the characters through the shaping language. The images he created for the role models of the times, such as *The Portrait of Fang Zhimin* created for Fang Zhimin Cadre

Figure 1. Lv Pinchang. *On Site No.1 Qianlong Blue and White*. Installation Foamed ceramic, 150×86×60cm, 2024

Figure 2. Lv Pinchang. *A Fu No.8 Flute-Playing*. Pottery, 42×42×55cm, 1994.

College in Jiangxi Province, *The Portrait of Jiao Yulu* created for Jiao Yulu Cadre College in Henan Province, *The Portrait of Huang Wenxiu* created for the “July 1st Medal” winners at Beijing Normal University, and *The Portrait of Yuan Longping* created for Yuan Longping, the father of hybrid rice, academician of the Chinese Academy of Engineering and recipient of the Republic Medal can all be regarded as fine works of sculpture portraits. The difficulty lies in how to mobilize and give play to the artistic plasticity of sculpture on the basis of the character prototype, which seems easy but is full of generalization and exaggeration.

In fact, the generation of sculptors represented by Lv Pinchang was faced not only with the inheritance of monument sculpture, but also with the huge challenges

posed by contemporary art in relation to traditional sculpture art. They were not satisfied with the creation of commemorative sculptures in the general sense, although this was already very difficult. Under the scourge and challenge of the contemporary visual culture trend, creating commemorative sculptures for history or public figures undoubtedly had publicity or field-specific characteristics, but also dissolved the independence of artists’ thinking and was more difficult to cope with during the rise of contemporary art in terms of thinking forms.

The most important artistic concept in contemporary art lies in how to show the activity and creativity of artists’ thinking by means of ready-made objects or all kinds of artistic media, so as to highlight artists’ ingeni-

Figure 3. Lv Pinchang. *Space Program No.5*. Metal and ceramic, 2006.

Figure 4. Lv Pinchang. *Three Pure Reflections of the Moon*. Bronze and stainless steel, 3200×460×23200cm, Shangrao city, Jiangxi province, 2010.

Figure 5. Lv Pinchang. *Bound Form No.3*. Steel-jade porcelain, 66×45×32cm, 2016.

ous use of media and the conceptual nature of “Tao in broken tiles”—exploring profound philosophical thinking from any ordinary object.

The difference between Lv Pinchang and traditional sculptors lies in his transcendence and rebellion. His sculpture education started with his study experience at Jingdezhen Ceramic Institute (now Jingdezhen Ceramic University), but he did not indulge in the study of traditional ceramic art. His master’s thesis “On the Aesthetic Quality of Ceramic Defect Textures” is regarded as his artistic declaration challenging the traditional ceramic aesthetic standards, and this declaration also laid the ideological foundation for his exploration of the contemporary art transformation of ceramic media.

If it is said that the sinicization of Western realistic sculpture enabled him to create a series of large-scale commemorative monuments with historical themes, which is his artistic odyssey starting from ceramic art and realizing his dream of becoming a sculptor, then ceramic art, as the mother body of Chinese sculpture culture, has always been his channel of rebirth for returning to the essence of art and native culture.

What is most characteristic of his artistic exploration is exactly how to transform ceramic art into contemporary art. For example, the *A Fu* series is his re-exploration of

folk art. He hopes to use the softness, extensibility and plasticity of clay to maximize the sense of expansion and fullness in folk sculpture. Also, the *Chinese Freehand Series*, which has continued from the 1980s to the present, reflects his attempt to stay away from busy work and secular life by creating the freehand image of “me” and thus reach an inner peace like the “Peach Blossom Spring.” In his works, he is transformed into monks, literati, and artists. The conceptual nature lies in cleverly using and splicing together the ready-made objects he collected during his travels and the “me” in the sculpture, creating the ancient lifestyle of lying and traveling to realize the unceasing literati concerns and spiritual ideals in his heart.

Obviously, ceramics is the medium that shapes Lv Pinchang’s art with individuality, yet it is also highly characteristic of Chinese local culture. This is the most distinct symbolic manifestation of his return to the artistic homeland. Here, there is both the paper-like art as thin as cicada’s wings—*Touching the World: Society*, and the huge *Space Program* series that makes people feel heavy. In the *Space Program* series, he wraps ceramic and metal materials around each other, creating a visual perception of weight tension through the combination of the five elements of earth and gold. The clever integration

Figure 6. Lv Pinchang. *Bound Form No.9*. Steel-jade porcelain, 149×45×28cm, 2016.

Figure 7. Lv Pinchang. *Bound Form: Bi No.2, 3, 4*. Steel-Jade Porcelain, 73×72×15cm, 2017.

of abstract geometric forms and naturally flawed textures highlights the warm, rustic quality of the clay material, shaped by its incompleteness and randomness, in stark contrast to the smooth, mirror-like surface and cold, hard nature of stainless steel. This comparison is precisely the visual collision between agricultural civilization and industrial civilization generated by the intertextual effect of the medium itself and ready-made objects. Although

Space Program has the implication of human conquest of nature, it also has the deeper metaphor that human beings must abide in harmonious coexistence with nature.

Lv Pinchang's use of ceramic media embodies the proposition of how contemporary art returns to traditional culture. In 2024, he created the series of variable installation works *On Site*. The works always present virtual archaeological excavation sites. The works semi-

Figure 8. Lv Pinchang. *On-Site No. Song*. Found objects and foamed ceramic, 150×86×60cm, 2024.

melt the ready-made objects through high temperature firing of ceramics, and these ready-made objects contain composite modern product waste such as porcelains, pottery, metals, and fireproof vessels. The image of this site expresses the archaeological excavation of post-modern life, because post-modern civilization sites will eventually become the historical civilizations buried deep underground. Through these civilization fragments, the works attempt to reveal the deep relationships between historical and contemporary, characteristics and spirits.

Lv Pinchang's artistic journey began in Jingdezhen, the ancient city known as the Pottery Capital. In 1995, he was introduced as a talented individual and transferred to CAFA, where he established the ceramics studio in the Sculpture Department, initiating the expansion and enrichment of CAFA's sculpture discipline construction. With the integration of disciplines and the teaching reform of the studio system in the Sculpture Department at the turn of the new century, Lv Pinchang has always been deeply involved in front-line teaching. He has sought a balance between art education and creation in his personal creations, teaching, and research, with the contemporary development of Chinese sculpture and the construction of local culture under the backdrop of globalization always running through his work.

During his tenure as the head of the Sculpture Department at CAFA, he actively promoted the compre-

hensive development of teaching the sculpture discipline. He built several influential national youth sculpture creation platforms, created a brand new model for Chinese sculpture education, and became a tremendous influence in the field of sculpture education. He successively planned and established academic brands, such as the Zeng Zhushao Sculpture Art Scholarship. To promote the development of youth sculpture aesthetic education, he planned and implemented projects like the *National Youth Sculpture Exhibition*, and in order to promote and advance the diverse Chinese sculpture cause, he and his colleagues created the model of the Chinese Contemporary Sculpture Biennial, planning and implementing events such as the *Datong International Sculpture Biennial*.

In October 2020, Lv Pinchang embarked on a new artistic journey. Invited by the Jiangxi Provincial Committee, he took up the post of Deputy Party Secretary and Vice President (in charge of administrative work) at Jingdezhen Ceramic University, becoming the true helmsman of the only university in the country named after ceramics. His artistic journey has returned to its starting point, yet this starting point significantly indicates the true belonging of his art.

November 28, 2024, in the 22nd Courtyard Street Art District, Beijing

SHANG HUI, is the Director of the Art Theory Committee of the China Artists Association and Distinguished Professor at the School of Fine Arts, Capital Normal University.

LV PINCHANG, born in 1962 in Shangrao, Jiangxi Province, graduated from the Sculpture Department of Jingdezhen Ceramic Institute (under the Ministry of Light Industry) in 1982 and furthered his studies at the Sculpture Department of Zhejiang Academy of Fine Arts (now China Academy of Art) from 1982 to 1983, earning his Master's degree in 1988. He currently serves as Deputy Party Secretary and Vice President of Jingdezhen Ceramic University (responsible for presiding over administrative affairs), Chairman of Jiangxi Artists Association, Vice President of China Urban Sculpture Association, Council Member and Director of the Public Art Committee of China Artists Association, Member of the National Committee

for Major Thematic Art Creation, Vice Director and Secretary-General of the Sculpture Art Committee of China Artists Association, Vice Director of the Art Committee of the National Urban Sculpture Guidance Committee, Vice President of China Sculpture Institute, Director of the Ceramic Professional Committee and Member of the Sculpture Committee at China Culture Promotion Society, and Distinguished Sculptor at both the Chinese Sculpture Academy of Chinese National Academy of Arts and the Sculpture Academy of China National Academy of Painting. Previously, he held the positions of Deputy Dean of the School of Plastic Arts and Director of the Sculpture Department at the Central Academy of Fine Arts. Honored with the Government Expert Allowance from the State Council since 1992, he is also a member of the International Academy of Ceramics (IAC).

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